

ISic1628

Funerary inscription for Jason the Elder

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 268

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 14.5 cm

Width 16.5 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 5-20 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

Edition: PHI178073

1. Ἰάσων πρεσβύτε-
2. ρος, μηδέν ζημι-
3. ώσας τήν έντολ-
4. ήν, ήγόρασεν έαυ-
5. τῷ και τοῖ[ς] τέκν-
6. ος έαυτοῦ τή-
7. ν κοῦπαν ταύτ-
8. ην.

Edition: PHI316297

1. Ἰάσων πρεσβύτε-
2. ρος μηδέν ζημι-
3. ώσας τήν έντολ-
4. ήν ήγόρασεν έαυ-
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7. ν κοῦπαν ταύτ-

8. ην.

9.

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Jason the Elder, in no way infringing the law, bought for himself and his children this burial place.

Translation (it)

Jason il presbitero, non violando la legge in alcun modo, ha acquistato per sé e per i suoi figli questo luogo di sepoltura.

Commentary

Jason is a common Jewish name. Presbyter simply means 'elder', but in this context signifies membership of a council of elders. It is not certain that this text is Jewish, but the word entole is a distinctively Jewish term in epitaphs, signifying the Mosaic law. The word koupa is very rare in Greek (two out of three other instances also from Catania), transliterating the Latin cupa, which generally describes a tomb in the shape of a half-barrel (cut lengthways). It is common to record the purchase of the burial space in this way.

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